

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 30, No. 13

Dear Readers,

At the end of this year, it gives me great pleasure to announce the twelfth regular issue of 2024. In this issue, various topical aspects of computer science are covered in 5 articles by 14 authors from 5 countries. I would like to thank all the authors for their sound research and the editorial board for the highly valuable review effort and suggestions for improvement. These contributions, together with the generous support of the consortium members, maintain the quality of our journal. I am looking forward to continuing my work as Managing Editor-in-Chief with the J.UCS community also in 2025.

In an ongoing effort to further strengthen our journal, I would like to expand the editorial board: If you are a tenured associate professor or above with a strong publication record, you are welcome to apply to join our editorial board. We are also interested in high-quality proposals for special issues on new topics and trends. Please consider yourself and encourage your colleagues to submit high-quality articles or special issue proposals to our journal. Finally, we are preparing to join the KOALA Cluster for Computer Science and Mathematics, making some minor organizational adjustments. We are switching to the CC BY license, and all metadata is accessible under the CC0 license. We are very grateful for the financial support for the next three years.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce the following 5 accepted articles: Marija Kuštelega, Renata Mekovec, and Ahmed Shareef from Croatia have conducted a systematic literature review to find out how the current research on the digital twin implementations has been positioned in front of practical challenges focused on privacy and security issues. Mehtap Ülker and A. Bedri Özer from Türkiye address in their research a fine-tuning BART-based model which generates a scientific summary by selecting important words from the text of the input document. Alessandro Osorio, Paulo Roberto Ferreira Jr., and Gerson Geraldo H. Cavaleiro from Brazil introduce a case study conducted with undergraduate and graduate students in Computer Science, involving guided reading of scientific papers, and recording students' perceptions of adherence to a set of guidelines for the presentation of scientific results. Ruan Visser, Trieko Grobler, and Marcel Dunaiski from South Africa address the gap in natural language processing for Southern African languages, and present an in-depth analysis of language model development under resource-constrained conditions. Last but not least, Seyedeh Aridis Ahadi, Kian Jazayeri, and Sahand Tebyani from Cyprus propose in their research an integrated framework for the identification of suicidal thoughts in social media through the implementation of a

layered classifier model consisting of a convolutional neural network (CNN) and a long short-term memory (LSTM) model.

Season greetings to all of you, relaxing holidays and 'Enjoy Reading'!

Best regards,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Christian Gütl', with a stylized flourish at the end.

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